

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CONTEMPORARY APPROACHES IN THE MEDICAL AND SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE APPENDICITIS

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Abstract

Acute appendicitis is one of the most common general surgical emergencies worldwide, with an increasing incidence, and pediatric appendectomy represents the most frequent abdominal procedure in this category.

The specialized literature highlights significant gaps in the optimal management of the condition, including decisions between surgical and conservative treatment, timing of intervention, indications for interval appendectomy, preoperative preparation, surgical approach in high-risk patients (open versus laparoscopic), intraoperative techniques, postoperative use of antibiotics, and the necessity of drain placement.

Although open appendectomy remains the classical standard, laparoscopic surgery has become increasingly utilized, offering advantages such as reduced surgical trauma, improved visualization of abdominal organs, and lower rates of postoperative complications. However, the applicability of laparoscopy in complicated appendicitis and the secure closure of the appendiceal stump remain subjects of debate.

In conclusion, despite being well-studied, acute appendicitis continues to generate controversy regarding the optimal therapeutic approach, with the literature often reporting conflicting results.

Keywords: acute appendicitis, pediatric appendectomy, laparoscopic surgery, open appendectomy, appendiceal stump closure, surgical management, postoperative complications.

Acute appendicitis represents one of the most common indications for emergency abdominal surgery in children worldwide, with appendectomy being considered the traditional standard of treatment. Errors in diagnosing this condition may lead either to appendectomies performed on a normal appendix or to missed cases of appendicitis – situations that constitute some of the main reasons for malpractice litigation, particularly in the United States [69].

The specialized literature contains numerous gaps regarding the optimal management of acute appendicitis, including decisions related to the preferred therapeutic option (surgical versus conservative), the optimal timing for performing appendectomy, the indications and timing of interval appendectomy, preoperative management, the choice of surgical approach in high-risk patients (open versus laparoscopic), intraoperative techniques, and the use of antibiotics in the postoperative period [82, 17]. The American College of Surgeons' National Surgical Quality Improvement Program – Pediatrics (NSQIP-P) has defined the intraoperative criteria for complicated appendicitis, including appendicitis with gangrenous changes, necrosis, or visible perforation of the appendix, intraperitoneal abscess, extraluminal fecalith, and diffuse fibrinopurulent exudate. Approximately 25–30% of appendicitis cases in children are complicated and represent the main cause of morbidity and increased utilization of medical resources [29, 50].

According to international guidelines, surgical intervention is recommended for early-stage complicated acute appendicitis (duration of symptoms ≤ 72 hours), including cases of periappendiceal phlegmon. In contrast, advanced stages of complicated appendicitis (du-

ration of symptoms >72 hours) or cases with periappendiceal abscesses are usually managed conservatively, through percutaneous drainage and administration of antibiotics [51].

Patients with complicated forms of acute appendicitis (appendiceal phlegmon or abscess) generally require appendectomy to relieve symptoms and prevent complications such as peritonitis. Surgical intervention may be performed early (immediately or a few days after admission) or delayed (several weeks later, following conservative treatment). However, the optimal timing for appendectomy in cases of appendiceal phlegmon or abscess remains a debated issue [94, 93]. In this context, there is a lack of robust data regarding the outcomes of patients with complicated acute appendicitis who are treated surgically instead of through a conservative approach. Evaluating the benefits and risks associated with each therapeutic option is essential, highlighting the need for further research and the development of optimized protocols to improve clinical outcomes [52].

The option of non-operative treatment for acute appendicitis is not a recent concept. The first documented case of spontaneous resolution of complicated acute appendicitis was published in 1910 by Smith and Wood Jones. Later, in 1930, Bailey proposed his own algorithm for non-surgical treatment, and in 1959 Coldrey first described a significant series of 471 patients treated conservatively with intravenous antibiotics [15, 91].

Currently, cases of uncomplicated acute appendicitis can be effectively treated with antibiotics until complete resolution of the disease and patient discharge, a concept widely discussed in the scientific lit-

erature [56, 18]. If antibiotic treatment can cure the disease, it would be reasonable to consider that surgical intervention may no longer represent an immediate emergency.

However, the main concern remains the timing of appendectomy, as there is a risk that non-perforated appendicitis may progress to perforation in cases where surgery is delayed. Some studies have confirmed that prolonged in-hospital waiting time before surgery is associated with a higher rate of perforation in children [75]. According to some studies, approximately one-third of patients initially treated with antibiotics subsequently required appendectomy, while two-thirds avoided surgery over the course of one year; however, the available evidence remains uncertain [22]. Although the cure rate with conservative treatment is lower than that achieved through surgery, antibiotics represent a reasonable option for patients with uncomplicated acute appendicitis who wish to avoid surgery and do not present additional risk factors [54, 87].

Recent meta-analyses have shown that antibiotics as an initial treatment for children with uncomplicated appendicitis may be feasible and effective without increasing the risk of complications. Nevertheless, the failure rate of conservative treatment – mainly determined by the presence of an appendicolith – is higher than that associated with appendectomy, and surgical intervention remains recommended in such situations [34, 12]. During the initial hospitalization, conservative treatment may fail in approximately 8% of cases, and up to 20% of patients may require readmission for recurrent appendicitis [60].

Therefore, emergency appendectomy remains the standard approach for the treatment of acute appendicitis, particularly in complicated cases [43]. Although gangrenous appendicitis is often considered together with perforated appendicitis, some studies suggest that the risk of postoperative infection in gangrenous appendicitis is comparable to that of simple appendicitis. In such situations, treatment without postoperative antibiotics may be appropriate, contributing to a reduction in the length of hospital stay and antibiotic use without significantly increasing the risk of infections or readmissions [58].

A meta-analysis that included two randomized controlled clinical trials on complicated acute appendicitis showed that early appendectomy is recommended for children with perforated appendicitis without an abscess at presentation. In contrast, for children presenting with an intra-abdominal abscess, the controversy between early appendectomy and interval appendectomy persists, as there is no convincing evidence indicating major differences between the two approaches. This situation highlights the need for high-quality randomized studies to clarify the risks and benefits of surgical versus conservative treatment in complicated appendicitis [15, 91].

Before the advent of laparoscopic surgery, it was common practice to remove the appendix even when it appeared normal in order to prevent future diagnostic confusion, as the appendectomy scar could be misleading. The removal of a histologically normal appendix was referred to as a negative appendectomy. In the medical literature, the rate of negative appendectomy

varies between 1.8% and 46%, being higher in children. Although it may seem useful, negative appendectomy is associated with subsequent complications in approximately 6% of patients [39, 2]. In 10–20% of laparoscopic explorations performed for right lower quadrant abdominal pain, the appendix appears normal and no other intra-abdominal pathology is identified.

Opinions regarding the management of a normal-appearing appendix differ: some authors, in the case of adult patients, recommend its removal [23], while others consider that appendectomy is not justified [84]. Available data suggest that a macroscopically normal appendix may be left *in situ* during laparoscopy in children and adolescents with suspected appendicitis, without the need for a subsequent surgical intervention. However, these conclusions are based on a limited number of patients, and studies with larger cohorts are needed for validation [21]. At present, the identification of a macroscopically normal appendix during laparoscopy for right iliac fossa pain in children represents a clinical dilemma, as there is no universally accepted protocol, and the long-term consequences of leaving the appendix *in situ* remain unclear [2].

With regard to uncomplicated appendicitis, laparoscopic appendectomy remains the standard initial treatment. Faster recovery, reduced postoperative pain, and the prompt return of intestinal function compared with open surgery make this procedure the preferred approach in children [63].

In 1997, Horwitz J.R. and colleagues recommended avoiding laparoscopic appendectomy in children with a preoperative diagnosis of complicated appendicitis and suggested early conversion to open appendectomy in cases where a complicated form of the disease was identified intraoperatively during laparoscopy [32]. Over the years, the use of laparoscopy in patients with complicated appendicitis has remained controversial, with the main arguments against it being the increased duration of the surgical procedure and the higher risk of postoperative infectious complications, particularly in children [59]. However, recent literature suggests that laparoscopic appendectomy can be an effective and safe method even in children with complicated appendicitis. It offers a lower rate of complications compared with the conventional open approach and may be considered the first therapeutic option for all patients, although additional prospective randomized studies are required to validate these conclusions [1].

Laparoscopic appendectomy has become the gold standard in the surgical treatment of appendicitis in children. The conventional procedure involves the use of three ports, one of which is inserted “open” through an infraumbilical incision and used for the introduction of the optical device. Pneumoperitoneum is achieved by CO₂ insufflation, maintaining the pressure between 10 and 12 mmHg. Under direct visualization, the other two operative trocars are inserted – one in the left flank and the other at the suprapubic level – providing access to the operative field [10].

Laparoscopic anatomy presents several particularities. The optical axis placed at the umbilical level initially determines visualization of the cecum, which may

obscure the appendix. To identify the base of the appendix, the anterior taenia coli is followed. Complete exposure of the appendix may require mobilization of the cecum and the omentum, as well as division of certain adhesions. Tilting the operating table to the left facilitates exposure of the appendix, while the mobility of the cecum is variable; in the case of a retrocecal appendix, division of the peritoneum in the right paracolic space may be necessary. The inflammation caused by acute appendicitis may alter anatomical landmarks and complicate the correct identification of the appendix [80].

After identifying the appendix and freeing it from the existing adhesions, resection of the appendiceal mesentery is performed, usually using bipolar forceps or a monopolar hook. The essential step of laparoscopic appendectomy consists of securing the base of the appendix, which is typically achieved using linear staplers, endoscopic loops, or polymer clips. More recently, clipless and sutureless appendectomy using a harmonic scalpel has been introduced. Each technique has its own specific advantages and disadvantages. The excised appendix is removed through the umbilical trocar, after which the abdominal cavity is carefully explored, any collections are evacuated, and in cases of gangrenous appendicitis with abundant purulent material, a tubular drain is placed through one of the 5-mm ports [10].

Laparoscopic appendectomies performed in children in complicated cases may be associated with intraoperative complications caused by technical difficulties during the dissection of a cecal appendix with advanced inflammation. In such situations, choosing the site where dissection begins is essential, because anatomical distortions and fibrosis may make the recognition of structures difficult, requiring the surgeon to start dissection in the least affected area. An alternative to the conventional antegrade laparoscopic technique in complicated cases is retrograde laparoscopic appendectomy, which involves initiating the dissection at the base of the appendix. This approach has proven to be technically feasible, allows optimal access to the appendix, and reduces the risk of excessive or unnecessary dissection in cases of complicated appendicitis [64].

However, there is significant variability between centers regarding the surgical approaches to appendicitis in children. In this context, some authors have proposed alternatives to the conventional three-port laparoscopic approach, such as single-incision laparoscopic appendectomy, which has become increasingly utilized due to its less invasive nature. Nevertheless, this technique has some disadvantages, including greater technical difficulty and longer operative times. In the literature, two main single-incision approaches for acute appendicitis in children have been described: the conventional technique, which involves intracorporeal management of the appendix, and laparoscopic-assisted transumbilical appendectomy with pneumoperitoneum, in which the appendix is exteriorized through the umbilicus for extracorporeal resection [86, 88, 62]. The laparoscopic-assisted transumbilical technique involves the insertion of an "open" trocar through an infraumbilical incision, followed by CO₂ insufflation to

establish pneumoperitoneum. Systematic exploration of the abdominal cavity is performed using an operative laparoscope, and the appendix is grasped with an atraumatic laparoscopic instrument and pulled through the umbilical incision, together with the cecum if it is mobile. In the presence of adhesions between the appendix, cecum, and peritoneum, these are released using bipolar forceps or a monopolar hook. Appendiceal resection is then performed outside the abdominal cavity using conventional techniques: ligation of the appendicular vessels, ligation of the appendiceal stump base, excision of the appendix, and burying of the stump by creating a pouch. The cecum is then repositioned, and a subsequent laparoscopy allows evaluation of cecal integrity, potential bleeding, and the presence of any intra-abdominal contents. In situations where transumbilical laparoscopic-assisted appendectomy cannot be safely performed due to inadequate exposure or exteriorization through the umbilical incision – for example, in cases with unclear anatomy, adhesions, an inflamed appendiceal mass, or retrocecal/subserosal position – conversion to open appendectomy is recommended [10, 49].

Of particular interest is the laparoscopic-assisted transumbilical appendectomy without pneumoperitoneum in children, proposed by Yamaoka B. et al. (2025) [88]. This method may represent a safe alternative to conventional laparoscopic appendectomy; however, several aspects require further discussion. First, patients with perforated appendicitis and abscess formation were excluded from the study, which limits the scope of application, although the technique could be relevant in complicated cases where pneumoperitoneum presents increased risks for the patient. Another consideration relates to the reported operative times, which were significantly longer than those for conventional multiport laparoscopic appendectomy. The prolonged duration of surgery may raise concerns regarding surgical efficiency, anesthesia safety, and decision thresholds for conversion. Additionally, the interpretation of elevated inflammatory markers as predictors of conversion represents an important point that requires careful evaluation [37].

Efficient and safe closure of the appendiceal stump is an essential step for preventing serious postoperative complications [36]. One of the most important differences between laparoscopic and open appendectomy lies precisely in the method used to seal the appendiceal stump. This step is critical, and errors can lead to severe complications such as stump dehiscence, fistulas, peritonitis, and sepsis [48]. In traditional open appendectomy, either ligation and inversion of the stump into the cecum or ligation of the base without inversion is performed. In the technique with stump inversion, risks have been reported, including perforation of the cecal wall, abscess formation in the stump, and deformation of the Bauhin valve [77].

In laparoscopic appendectomy, there are multiple options for occluding the appendiceal stump. Although there is no unanimous consensus on the preferred method, several techniques have been successfully applied in practice without increasing the rate of intraoperative or postoperative complications [24]. All methods used for stump closure appear to provide a

similar level of safety. However, the degree of appendiceal inflammation and the surgeon's experience with laparoscopic technique influence the choice of the optimal method. Stump closure can be achieved using a manually tied loop, which has proven to be a safe and cost-effective method. Nevertheless, ligating the appendix can be technically challenging in children due to the limited working space available during laparoscopy [6, 89].

In cases of complicated acute appendicitis, particularly gangrenous or perforated forms, the appendiceal base may be morphopathologically compromised, making closure difficult and increasing the risk of serious complications such as appendiceal stump dehiscence, with subsequent fecal peritonitis or fistula formation. Inflammation and necrosis may extend to the surrounding cecal wall, preventing standard ligation. In such situations, several alternative options have been proposed, including placement of a cecostomy tube, partial cecal resection, or right hemicolectomy [90, 13].

Postoperative purulent intra-abdominal complications directly associated with the efficacy of appendiceal stump closure have been reported in 1.85–4% of cases, and necrosis of the appendiceal stump base was documented in 2.54% of cases [27, 71]. In laparoscopic procedures for complicated appendicitis with a compromised appendiceal base, some studies reported postoperative intra-abdominal abscess in 16.7%, ileus in 7.4%, and surgical site infection in 7.4%, while appendiceal stump fistula was observed in a single case [26].

In 1991, Cristalli B.G. and colleagues published the first report on the use of titanium clips in 20 patients, who were discharged on the fifth postoperative day without complications [16]. Titanium clips have proven to be safe and effective for securing the appendiceal base, offering advantages over stapling devices by providing the same biocompatibility at a comparatively lower cost [19, 81].

Several recent studies have shown that the rate of infectious complications is not significantly influenced by the method of appendiceal stump closure, whether using an endoloop or an endostapler. Routine closure with an endoloop is a safe, simple, and cost-effective procedure, even in cases of complicated appendicitis [95]. However, in perforated appendicitis, the use of an endostapler has been associated with a lower incidence of postoperative intra-abdominal abscess and postoperative ileus, as well as reduced rates of readmission and reoperation [25].

Meta-analyses suggest that appendiceal stump closure during laparoscopic appendectomy is feasible and safe with both endostapler and endoloop, even in complicated appendicitis. The use of an endostapler has been associated with a reduced incidence of superficial wound infection in children [14]. However, given the higher costs, the endostapler should be reserved for cases in which the stump cannot be safely secured with an endoloop or Hem-o-lok [24]. The use of non-absorbable polymer ligation systems, such as Hem-o-lok®, for securing the appendiceal stump offers several advantages, including simple application, wide availability, relatively low cost, and reduced operative time [41, 4]. However, Hem-o-lok clips are not recommended in cases of complicated appendicitis, such as perforation

or inflammation of the appendiceal base, or when the appendiceal lumen is large, due to an increased risk of complications [74].

The use of Endo GIA for securing the appendiceal stump is limited by its high cost and the need for an additional port or replacement of the 10-mm suprapubic port to introduce the device. Additionally, the foreign materials used for stump fixation can trigger inflammatory reactions in the abdominal cavity, potentially leading to the development of adhesive intestinal obstruction [78, 92]. In recent years, several studies have reported on the effectiveness of sutureless appendectomy using devices such as the harmonic scalpel and the LigaSure™ bipolar coagulator [11]. Recent evaluations comparing the safety and efficacy of LigaSure™ versus Endoloop for appendiceal stump closure in pediatric laparoscopic appendectomy have shown that LigaSure™ is a safe and effective alternative, providing reliable sealing even in cases of complicated appendicitis [42].

The harmonic scalpel is also a safe and effective alternative for stump closure, offering improved surgical outcomes and faster recovery. Its use significantly reduces operative time, postoperative pain, complication rates, length of hospital stay, and the need for readmission, thereby improving postoperative recovery and outcomes [47]. A major advantage of these modern techniques is the elimination of complications associated with foreign bodies. The harmonic scalpel, powered by ultrasonic energy, can be used in both open and laparoscopic procedures for dissection, cutting, and sealing of tissues, serving as a versatile instrument that allows all these steps to be performed single-handedly.

Controversy persists regarding the usefulness of peritoneal drainage and irrigation, with recent literature, including Cochrane reviews and randomized studies, questioning the routine use of drains, particularly in uncomplicated appendicitis [44]. Peritoneal irrigation was first described in 1906 by Hotchkiss L.W., who noted: "Probably no issue in modern surgery is of greater interest and importance, and about which there is more disagreement, than the treatment of diffuse peritonitis. The absolute impossibility of draining the general peritoneal cavity does not seem evident enough to many surgeons, and the nature of the peritoneal response to drainage is only imperfectly understood." In cases of acute appendicitis, he proposed free irrigation of the pelvis and lower abdominal cavity with hot saline solution and placement of a small "cigarette-type" drain at the site of the removed appendix [33]. Over the years, this technique became widespread in abdominal surgery [65].

In appendectomy procedures, peritoneal irrigation aims to physically remove pus, necrotic tissue, fecal matter, and other infectious sources to reduce bacterial load and minimize the risk of postoperative intra-abdominal infections [45]. Some randomized studies have shown that superoxidized solution, used as an adjuvant therapy along with saline, can be safe and effective in reducing postoperative complications such as wound infection and pain, thereby contributing to faster recovery [73]. Additionally, some authors recommend peritoneal irrigation with antibiotics, superoxidized solutions, or specialized therapies such as intraperitoneal

chemotherapy and hyperthermic intraperitoneal chemotherapy, which have been shown to significantly reduce intra-abdominal infections and, in oncologic contexts, cancer cells when applied according to indications [31].

However, randomized clinical trials comparing wound irrigation with antibiotics versus irrigation with normal saline during open appendectomy have not demonstrated statistically significant benefits, indicating the need for further clinical validation [38, 72]. A recent study reported the local use of atomized povidone-iodine in small volumes as a new and feasible operative technique for laparoscopic appendectomy in complicated appendicitis in children [9].

Several studies have shown that peritoneal irrigation does not offer significant advantages compared with simple aspiration of peritoneal contents. In acute appendicitis, abdominal irrigation does not appear to reduce the incidence of intra-abdominal abscesses, leading to arguments in favor of avoiding routine peritoneal lavage in the treatment of perforated appendicitis in children. Nevertheless, there is a clear need for large-scale, multicenter randomized clinical trials to provide sufficient evidence for definitive conclusions. At present, the decision to perform peritoneal irrigation often depends on the surgeon's experience and is considered highly subjective [20, 61].

It is well known that children undergoing appendectomy for complicated appendicitis (gangrenous or perforated) have a higher predisposition to postoperative complications compared with those with uncomplicated appendicitis [57]. The placement of an intra-abdominal drain, both after open and laparoscopic appendectomy, has been considered beneficial for preventing postoperative intra-abdominal abscess formation, monitoring bleeding, and preventing appendiceal stump leaks. This practice was based on the widespread belief that the accumulation of inflammatory exudate in the abdominal cavity increases the risk of postoperative complications, including intra-abdominal abscesses, appendiceal stump leaks, wound infections, and intestinal obstructions [85].

However, the routine use of postoperative abdominal drainage remains controversial. Multiple sources of evidence, including Cochrane studies, suggest that routine drainage after various abdominal procedures is not essential [79]. The effect of drainage on preventing intra-abdominal abscesses or wound infection after open appendectomy is uncertain, and the degree of intra-abdominal contamination appears to play a more significant role in the development of complications [35, 3].

In laparoscopic appendectomy for patients with perforated appendicitis, some studies support that abdominal drain placement is safe and effective, and early removal within the first 48 hours is associated with lower postoperative complication rates, shorter hospital stays, and reduced costs [30]. However, other studies have shown that intraperitoneal drainage after laparoscopic appendectomy for complicated appendicitis does not provide additional benefits in preventing abscesses and may prolong hospitalization [57, 5].

There is also the view that pelvic drainage may provide real clinical benefits in selected cases, when the

decision is guided by intraoperative findings and the surgeon's clinical judgment [7]. Consequently, high-quality clinical trials and prospective registries are needed to define the patient groups who might benefit from intraoperative drainage and to optimize practical protocols, including the type of drain, management method, and timing of removal [40].

Preoperative administration of antibiotics in uncomplicated appendicitis has demonstrated clear benefits, including reduced hospital stay and improved clinical outcomes. In addition, preoperative antibiotic therapy appears to slow disease progression, allowing safe postponement of surgery without increasing the risk of complications [76].

Postoperative antibiotic therapy is an additional option used to prevent postoperative infectious complications. The most common complications include intra-abdominal abscess, occurring in approximately 1.5–7.9% of patients after appendectomy, and surgical site infections, observed in 3.4–10.0% of cases. Evidence regarding postoperative antibiotic therapy is limited, and the optimal duration of treatment remains a matter of debate [83].

There is no consensus on the ideal duration of antibiotic therapy; most guidelines recommend treatment for 3 to 7 days. However, shorter courses may be equally effective in preventing infectious complications [66]. Decisions regarding the route of antibiotic administration should be individualized, taking into account patient characteristics, intraoperative findings, and the response to initial therapy [70].

Although the advantages of laparoscopy in pediatric surgery are well established, there is some discussion regarding the physiological effects of pneumoperitoneum, created by insufflation of CO₂ to establish working space in the peritoneal cavity. This can induce significant changes in respiratory and cardiovascular function, including decreased preload and cardiac output, alterations in heart rate and blood pressure, increased ventilation requirements, and reduced urine output, especially in infants. Other systemic effects include CO₂ absorption, stimulation of the neurohumoral vasoactive system, reduced renal blood flow, and impaired renal function [53].

Laparoscopic techniques have significantly reduced morbidity associated with appendectomy. Nevertheless, surgical treatment of appendicitis carries certain risks, including exposure to general anesthesia, wound infections, postoperative pain, accidental injury to intra-abdominal structures, and the possibility that these complications may occur in the context of a negative appendectomy. These considerations have fueled interest in non-operative management of uncomplicated acute appendicitis in children. Several recent studies have shown that this strategy can be a reasonable alternative, with one-year success rates of 70–85% [68].

However, some research has shown that in cases of uncomplicated appendicitis in children, non-operative treatment has significantly higher failure rates compared with surgical intervention, without substantial clinical benefits on secondary outcomes. These findings support surgery as the current treatment of choice [46].

Although laparoscopic appendectomy is considered the gold standard for acute appendicitis, conversion to an open procedure may be necessary in certain situations. Studies have identified six independent risk factors for conversion, including two preoperative factors – elevated white blood cell count and increased C-reactive protein levels – and four intraoperative factors – the presence of perforation, necrosis or gangrene, perityphlitic abscess, and peritonitis [8]. Reported conversion rates reach up to 19.8%, with common causes being dense adhesions, poor visualization, and intraoperative bleeding [67].

An emerging approach is endoscopic transcecal appendectomy, which is still in its preliminary stages. This technique has not been widely adopted due to the lack of guidelines on procedural protocols and patient selection. Its theoretical advantages include direct assessment of appendiceal orifice lesion extent, preservation of the ileocecal valve and adjacent colon, more direct access to the appendix, and reduced risk of injury to surrounding structures – particularly relevant in patients with prior abdominal surgery and adhesions. Additionally, this technique offers cosmetic benefits, avoiding surgical scars and incision-related complications such as hernias and wound infections [28, 55].

In conclusion, although acute appendicitis is a common and extensively studied condition, numerous uncertainties persist regarding the optimal diagnostic and therapeutic strategy. Controversies concern the indication for conservative versus surgical treatment, the timing of intervention in cases of phlegmon or appendiceal abscess, the need for postoperative antibiotic therapy, the role of drainage, the ideal technique for appendiceal stump closure, and the lack of standardized protocols for immunocompromised or neutropenic patients.

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